

THE IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON STATE SOVEREIGNTY: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Sovereignty has always been the red line of a state that is never compromised or shared but on the other hand globalization has undermined or transformed it in 21st century. Therefore, The main goal of this paper is to understand the complex relationship between state sovereignty and globalization in 21st century rather than considering anyone as fixed. The study explains that sovereignty as transformative rather than eroded by globalization across the multiple scales. Moreover explaining these terms in the light of three major theories of International Relations such as Realism sees the sovereignty as fixed and power of state while liberalism explain it in the light of mutual cooperation and institutional governance and interdependence, on the other hand the Constructivists asserts that how ideas, norms and beliefs shape state sovereignty. The paper also shed light on the critiques of scholars on the globalization how it manipulates state behaviour in modern world through International Organizations and Institutions. Explain the nature of globalization whether it is transformative or selective. The study serves the case analysis including Iran's nuclear sanctions, Gaza's geopolitical context, the Ukraine conflict and economic reforms in India and china. And how states resists against the selective nature of globalization by major powers on states like Iran, North Korea and China. In last suggests the strategies and policies to protect the states sovereignty from external pressure in a Globalized world.

Keywords: State, Sovereignty, Globalization, International Relations, International Organizations

1.INTRODUCTION

The Globalization has been the major influential factor in developing the relations on global level, changing the nature of Politics, Economies, Cultures, Security structure and Environment on State level. The relationship between globalization and state sovereignty has been the confrontational debate in the contemporary world which has become the **De-territorialized** world by the Cross-border flow of capital, ideas, flood of information and communication. Despite being the plus point for the free economies, integrated world and human interaction with the rest of world but the cost payer is the traditional Westphalian state

system that sought the absolute control or authority in political, economic and social domains, non-intervention in their respective territory but that is compromised by the emergence of multinational corporations and international organizations by imposing their rules to reshape their authority and treat their sovereignty as a win-win game that is violation of the rules of traditional state system. The debate critically analyses the question how the globalization undermines or reshape the state sovereignty according to its conditions in 21st century? Which will be discussed in different in multiple lenses of theories. As realist

asserts on the dominant role of state on the global level; liberal's emphasis on the rise of cooperation of institutional governance; constructivist says how evolution of norms redefine sovereignty itself? Moreover, the article will explain the complex interplay between the national autonomy and global governance in the 21st century. How trade financial standards, migration and regimes simultaneously constrain or empower the state functioning? And will discuss the strategies or policies do states implement to safeguard their sovereignty in the context of global pressure. The goal is to shed light on multiple angles in which state sovereignty is affected by globalization. Unlike studies that are confined to single dimension.

2. Literature Review

The existing literature, on the globalization and its impact on state sovereignty presents multiple dimensions like evolution of sovereignty and challenges posed by the globalization, has been discussed by many scholars. Perhaps, they have comprehensively explained the changing nature of states and their sovereignty with the passage of time by the growing influence of globalization.

The historical evolution of sovereignty from natural law to positive law, which was given by Jean Bodin in 16th century and used the term **Natural Law** supreme power over citizens who are not subject to limitations of any man-made law for Sovereignty in *les six Livres de la Republique* (1576). Moreover, the conceptual distinction between internal and external sovereignty that is shared now by the rise of international organizations such as the ICJ, ICC, UNO, WTO, and international tribunals that penetrates the domestic affairs like human rights, Environmental protection that has pressed the immunity of domestic jurisdiction. (Simonovic, 2000).

As Simonovic' wrote about the evolution of sovereignty, (Christian Volk, 2019) also emphasized the "bonding concept" that develops political, legal, and social dividing the world into binaries such as internal/external and national/international or simply hierarchical system. Moreover, critically analyze the debate between Carl Schmitt and Hans Kelsen. Schmitt prioritize the political decision and power while kelsen focused on the law-based order and hierarchy of norms. Therefore, Volk interprets that they both focus on the same structural power and supreme authority in different ways. Volk on the

contrary focuses on the contemporary debate between scholars Dieter Grimm and Jean Cohen. Grimm sees globalization as supranational governance that leads to the loss of sovereignty and democratic capacity, while Cohen argues for a transformation of sovereignty rather than its decline. (Volk, 2019)

Moreover, the authors such as (Elizabeth A. Oji and M.V.C Ozioko, 2012), see the globalization as multidimensional term that covers the political, social, economic, and technological process. That intensifies the interconnectedness and blurs the distinction between domestic and international politics and advanced the way of communication, transformation and information technology. And globalization weakens the national policy -makings by strengthening the IOs trough treaties, regulations and supervisory strategies. They also see how the diffusion of western values such as individualism, human rights and rational-legal authority by the cultural exchange that enrich societies and warned that cultural globalization weakens identities and cultural sovereignty due to the expansion of global media and communication technologies (Oji-Ozioko, 2012).

Additionally, Melanie U. Pooch (2016) stresses the globalization evolution and its effects. For globalization the Economists used the term of "Levitt" in 1983 which means the transnational interconnectedness of economies in 1990s. The first stimulus of globalization is discovery of America by Christopher Columbus, second the rise of communication in 19th century, third supranational economies. Cultures finally the most significant is the end of cold war resulted in the borderless world that affected the citizens by the flow of people and capital. Although the globalization has influenced the world but the third world countries are not even touched which entitles the globalization as an uneven force and unbalanced which is confined to only specific region that is known as the Western-globalization where the globalization has brought significant innovations that are the competitive markets and interconnected economies like NAFTA, IMF, World Bank, Wall Street, TNCs and MNCs. On the other hand the rise of "hybridization" that promotes diversity of cultures of multiple ethnicities where people are inspired from different cultures especially westernization. Moreover, the American neo-colonialism by their consumerism, commercial mechanism, mass

media and most important is their “Manifest destiny” that promotes morality and ideas of wrong/right and good/bad through Hollywood, hip hop and has brought the world under the umbrella of democracy. (Pooch, 2016)

Furthermore, Gunnar Folke Schuppert inspects the concept of sovereignty that shifted from societal powers (church and empires) and political powers explained by the legal-political thinkers like Hobbes and Machiavelli justified the state survival through absolute power to hierarchical control. Main focuses on the judicial supremacy, impose taxes, appoint officials, and declare war/peace stimulate states to have control on its jurisdiction. (Scuppert, 2021)

Besides all that Templeman in his work “Democracy under siege” argues the role of china’s BRI in Indo-pacific through debt-diplomacy supply chain eroding the sovereignty of regional democracies. Portrays the globalization on two levels: externally china shapes domestic coalition and wakens accountability but on the contrary the liberal democracies respond with coalition work like Quad alliances and “Free and Open Indo-pacific” (FOIP) and try to revive the liberal rules-based order alternative to Beijing. Perhaps most importantly distinguishes the Westphalian sovereignty which is affected in the case of Taiwan de facto autonomy with the interdependent/pool sovereignty and most popular democratic sovereignty which is transparent and accountable. (Templeman, 2020)

Economically “Li and Zhou” stresses on the financial globalization of capitalism, dominated the state economies and their control on state’s right to shape economies and regulates the institutions, neoliberal world. Added to that thy also focus on the transformation of industrial capitalism into Financial capitalism that affects the sovereignty of developing economies, like china in choosing their independent economic system, making independent financial policies (like exchange rate, money supply and interest rates). It is impossible to proceed with both fixed exchange rate, independent monetary policy and capital mobility cannot coexist his all problem is known as “impossible trinity”. Also criticize the neoliberalism’s role in 2008, 2011, and 2015 crisis. (Li-Zhou, 2015)

Besides above all scholars Grinin’s argues that globalization does not undermines the state sovereignty but states weakening their autonomy

for their economic, political, and security benefits. He also argues that Sovereignty is not fixed rather it changes due to global trends. In case of the regionalization and supranational governance (EU, ASEAN, AU) restructured sovereignty because states are in need to be the part of that institution for collective benefits what he tries to say in contemporary world voluntary sovereignty is reducing state autonomy. (Grinin, 2012)

Analyzing critically Makovetska et al. in which he quotes Troyan “who argues that globalization has blurred the internal-external autonomy like the Gulf war and EU expansion that illustrate the sovereignty is weakening or undermined”. Also explain the major threat to sovereignty in contemporary world is cyberspace that threatens the cybersecurity and disinformation. (Makovetska, 2024)

The above given literature review shows that the debate between two forces like sovereignty and globalization has always been conflictual and will always be. Different scholars have different views on both terms that sovereignty is not only affected by globalization but also by the voluntary nature of state that compromise on their sovereignty for their political, economic and social benefits.

However, all the work done by the international scholars do not cover all dimensions of the issue on the impact of globalization on state sovereignty which is the burning issue of modern world. There are still gaps that need to be filled. Therefore, there will be discussion on the contemporary issues regarding the impact of globalization on the state policy making in multiple domains.

Research objectives

- 1: to critically analyze the theoretical discourse of Realist, liberal and constructivist approach in explaining the impact of globalization on state sovereignty.
- 2: To critically examine the impacts of globalization whether it weakens or transforms state sovereignty in the 21st century.
- 3: To adopt the strategies and policies to safeguard the state sovereignty in the context of global pressure.

Research Design

The qualitative research methodology will be applied in this paper through different ideas of scholars like Realists (Hans Morgenthau, Jhon Mearsheimer, Kenneth Waltz), Liberals (Robert

Kohane, Joseph Nye) and Constructivists (Alexander Wendt) about the concepts of sovereignty and globalization and their impacts on each other these three theories will be applied to resolve these issues.

Globalization role in shaping the nature of sovereignty in the modern world and highly affects the autonomy of state in decision making described by different scholars like Simonovic, Volk, Evelyn Sophies, and Gunnar in their works. Therefore, in the lens of Realism, liberalism and constructivism the sovereignty and globalization will be critically analyzed. Additionally, the strategies and policies will be adopted to safeguard the sovereignty in the context of global pressure.

➤ **Theoretical lens: Explaining the concepts of Sovereignty and Globalization and their impacts on each other**

Sovereignty: sovereignty is defined by multiple ideas which are explained below...

Realism: Realism is all about power and survival in a world where states try to pursue their national/self-interests to protect themselves by gaining power in an anarchic world for their security which leads to competition. Realists Such as Thomas Hobbes in his work “**Leviathan**” sees the concept of sovereignty as the primary and supreme authority of state within their jurisdiction and unreachable by any external power. For realists the sovereignty is the legal and significant necessity in an anarchic international system.

Liberalism: A hopeful view that stipulates that states can work together to create and stable world through cooperation through International Organizations such as UNO, WTO, IMF for economic interests to decrease the ratio of wars and resolve global problems. Moreover, **Liberals** express the concept of sovereignty as less absolute and more flexible than realists suggest. According to them the states voluntarily diminish their sovereignty through the institution, agreements, and interdependence just for their national interests. Just as Kohane’s concept of **complex interdependence** which suggest that sovereignty is reshaped rather than eliminated. (Nye, Kohane, 1977)

Constructivism: It is different from above two mainstream theories that stresses on the power of ideas and beliefs in shaping that how states interacts. Ideas matters means that when states

considers each other as friends they are likely to cooperate. Additionally despite UK has 50 Nuclear Bombs but on the other hands North Korea’s five Nuclear Bombs are the major threats to West because of different ideas. That’s how Ideas matters. On the contrary side **constructivist** such as **Alexander Wendt** argues that “anarchy is what state see it”. It is a social constructed not an objective. It exists because states collectively believe in it due to their repeated interactions and shared understandings. (Mick O Brien, 2018)

Globalization: refers to the interconnectedness and interdependence of world economies, cultures, and governments. A process driven by movement of goods, services, capital information, and people across national boundaries facilitated by advance in technology, communication, and communication.

Realists describe, the globalization evades it by fostering interdependence exposes exploitation of states by major powers which leads to security dilemma and relative gains and NATO expansion as a threat to Russian sovereignty promoting to clashes like ongoing Russia-Ukraine war, as material factor driven by state interests and power dynamics. According to **Kenneth Waltz** an anarchic system does not allow and limits the globalization to change state behavior rather states are only actors to pursue relative interests in competitive environment (Pechlivanis, 2012). However, states are enduring the pressure of globalization to re assert their autonomy as we have the example of China in protecting their autonomy visa-vise getting benefits from globalization just because of their capacity to face globalization. Moreover, **Mearsheimer** on the other hand in his Book “The Tragedy of Great Power Politics” argues that economic interdependence and power competition influence policy making. States are engaged in global trade just to enhance their influence on global affairs. (A. Gul 2024)

Liberals posits that globalization is transformative and positive that promotes mutual cooperation, benefits in the network of actors across the borders. On the other hand, Nye sees globalization as promotion of **soft power** opportunities due to increase of interdependence through democratic means, economic ties via IGOs like UN and WTO, reducing conflicts through complex interdependence like pooled sovereignty of EU for political and economic stability that avoids wars by raising costs and empowers the institutions role in

managing the globalization by the opportunities like collective security like NATO under **Article 5** an attack on one is considered an attack on all. (Nye, Kohane, 1977). Moreover, **Moravcsik's** liberal ideas and focus on the Inter-governmentalism shows that the domestic alternatives shape state bargaining in the global affairs rather than undermining the state sovereignty. (Akilatan, 2021). In last states face challenges through institutional bodies such as the UK's referendum due to EU influence on decision-making of British just to regain their undermined sovereignty known as **Brexit** (Exit of British from European union) as to achieve their national objectives but unfortunately could not succeeded rather creating a single market or isolated but before the **brexit** UK had control on their stable economy and overcome their weaknesses which was positive point for UK economy. (DPhil, 2016) Therefore sometimes globalization also benefits states when they are not capable of enduring isolation but to regain their lost or compromised sovereignty states sometimes face challenges or pay the costs.

Constructivists finally focus on how states see globalization? And how human rights, environmental and developments ideas reshape nature of sovereignty? **Sikkink** explains that these ideas changed the state behavior when states interfered in other states for human rights was considered as violation of state autonomy, but the rise of transnational advocacy has made it legitimize this view. (Sikkink, 2018). Moreover, Alexander Wendt and Martha Fennimore expresses their idea as the concept of sovereignty is socially constructed through shared ideas rather than fixed material realities but promotes ideational and material factors. The cultural globalization has given rise to turbo consumerism that is used for personal happiness with the consumption of material possession. However, this term is used for relate capitalism but the society has given more, significance like the "Coca Colonization", in 1950s with the emergence of global brands that dominated the global market, used by French communists. Other like McDonaldization hub of fast food there are more companies but they are given name by the society. These all corporates are criticized by Naomi Klein a Canadian journalist. (Heywood, 2011)

Discussion and Critical Analysis on Globalization and State's Sovereignty

Debate between globalization and sovereignty is based on the conflicts and complex views of both sides whether it weakens or transform the state sovereignty in 21st century. This section of paper will critically evaluate the main arguments on both sides to develop the balanced conclusions. Moreover, we will critically analyze the theoretical discourse of realists, liberals, constructivists in explaining the aforementioned phenomena. Additionally fueling to the issue, will suggest policies and strategies to safeguard the sovereignty in the context of global pressure.

➤ **Globalization stimulates state sovereignty across, political, economic, cultural, legal, military, technological and environmental domains in 21st century rather it shapes then weakening it through interdependence and shared governance.**

The term globalization is used for the advancements in human history that comforted human in every aspect of life and the concept of sovereignty is **transformed** by the globalization with the passage of time. As in Middle Ages the concept of sovereignty was the unchallengeable Monarch and church just because these two institutions were considered the divine ones. That was changed by the **Treaty of Westphalia** that asserted the state to be absolute authority, with the rise of modern nation state, independent from external pressure that remained till WW2. (Ali Afyare, 2024) Moreover, in 1940s the rise of international organizations, regional institution and rise of third world after De-colonization that was major development of shaping the way for globalization and changing the nature of sovereignty in Bipolar world of America and soviet union between capitalists and communists these two ideologies became the factors of sovereignty for both powers and their allies. Additionally In the domain of **Technology** the development of Nuclear weapon and arms race between them that was known as **MAD** (Mutual Assured Destruction) and soviet technological advancement in the shape of Sputnik satellite in 1957 which was a major challenge for America and the emergence of World Wide Web (WWW) in 1991 which is the global information medium connected to internet. Perhaps more importantly the fall of **Bretton woods** that was characterized by the slogan of bigger-thy-neighbor but before that the Keynesian

model somehow gave state the authority to regulate the economies and state's protectionist policies but that was replaced by **Neo-liberal** world, that was major economic development in which institutions such as (IMF, WTO, GATT and World Bank), in economic domain played major role in shaping the state decision making through interconnected economies, Aid programs or loan to the developing states on certain conditions which compelled the states to compromise their sovereignty and give the authority to these institutions to make policies for them, cooperation through MNCs and TNCs, investment opportunities, and free trade these are now major interests of states. That is not enough the world engagement in the social platforms especially the westernization influenced the lifestyle and cultures, norms and beliefs of other worlds through Hollywood, K Dramas and many more by expanding their culture and ideologies. Therefore, one can argue that the nature of sovereignty is transformed from time to time just as states see their interests but sometimes it is also visible that globalization is selective which is promoted by major powers to impose it on the weak states. (Heywood, 2011)

The globalization is **discriminatory** to developing states except China affects them through the rise of International Organizations like the UNSC five permanent veto powers (USA, UK, RUSSIA, CHINA, FRANCE) hold the crucial powers to influence the global affairs and they often pursue their national interests by the help of these institutions and unequal treatments to the peripheries. (Martinez-Vela, 2001) After WW2 there was need for a platform where states would gather to avoid the future conflicts and promote peace and cooperation with the help of diplomacy but are used selectively for those who are the allies of the core the example is visible in the case of Gaza genocide after October 7 incident, despite majority of the states were in the favor of ceasefire but with the vetoes of USA in June, September, November 2025 just the goals of Israel were not achieved so as their **MIC** (Military industrial complex) that is biggest arms industries of USA and US. Military aid to Israel (\$130+ billion) that links to MIC interests and policy decisions. (Masters, Merrow, 2025) Therefore, the resolution could not pass. And no state can question if so then states will face the consequences of sanctions. For that some states argue that international system needs reforms to be addressed the inequalities and biasness of major

powers therefore the globalization is selective to the peripheries by applying world system theory.

Moreover, in case of Iran and sanctions imposed in 2015 with JCPOA nuclear limits including centrifuge caps, uranium stockpiles, and facility modifications like Arak by International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and have monitored 24-hours access to sites such as Fordow and Natanz with the help of cameras and satellite imagery due to that Iran faced the consequences in the shape of interconnected sanctions and trade pressure in a globalized world. This mechanism was the multilateral framework coordinated P5+1 (USA, UK, France, China, Russia, Germany) efforts. This was considered by Iran as discriminatory and ensuring the security of Israel and the major powers sought Iran effort as an aggressor in the region and threat to regional stability. EU and countries like Oman, Norway, and Japan Supported IAEA financially. But Iran did not compromise on their autonomy rather resisted and continued developing nuclear building project before June war with Israel Iran has reached to 60% of uranium Enrichment and accumulated 408 kilograms according IAEA. That resulted in US and Israel strikes on Iran nuclear facilities and severely damaged those sites. (Grossi's, 2025)

Politically, globalization influence sovereignty and has altered into pool sovereignty through rise of IGOs and supranational governments where states voluntarily compromise on sovereignty for collective benefits. UN and The regional Bodies like EU, ASEAN, and SAARC implement norms by the name of human rights security and policy coordination avoiding unilateral decisions which undermines the independent decision-making of states. Like European court has the right to cancel state laws and UN on the name of Right to Protect (R2P) justifies the intervention in independent states for humanitarian reasons. NGOs on other hand as a soft power ruling domestic policies such as amnesty schemes, ICRC, UNESCO and UNICEF. But in case of South Asia SAARC is not that much effective due to PAK-INDIA relations especially after may war and resisted on their sovereignty but less shaped by SCO (Shanghai Cooperation Organization) by China. (Ahmed Shah, 2025) EU role in Russian-Ukraine war is very important to discuss that how Europe and USA gave financial and **military** assistance support to Ukraine by imposing sanctions on Russia through European council and European commission. But

that support is just for the European interests and deter further Russian aggression and strengthening NATO's collective defense. US demands for minerals and to have control on those sites and Ukraine does not allow it. But recent news suggests that TRUMP has agreed to make a deal on peace plan and accept Russian control on occupied territories that is major question on the European Union and Ukraine's sovereignty. Therefore, the developing states pay the cost for the interests of major powers and International Organizations. (Kent, 2025)

Despite political domain the globalization has significant effect on the state sovereignty in economic domain by integrating national markets into Global markets, multilateral corporations, Foreign Direct Investment (FDIs), and Neo-liberal economic policies which promotes privatization and deregulations prioritizing global market at the expense of national interests. Like in the case of India 1991 economic balance of payment crisis IMF providing loans to India but on some conditions Like (LPG) economic reforms known as Liberalization, Privatization, and Globalization that led to profound impact. (S. Anklesaria Aiyar, 2016) Moreover, 2008 crisis in USA has led to global recession affected the global economies and compelled the governments and central banks to implement fiscal and monetary crisis for economic recovery. That happened due to the globalized economies which are connected and in a globalized world every single event in one corner of world has effect on the individual of other corner of world due to the institutions like IMF, WTO, World Bank. However, states like china take the advantage being the part of WTO as a "Free Rider" and currently US-China trade war highlights how economic interdependence exposes to external vulnerabilities especially the concerns on the sovereignty of Global South. (Chen, 2014) But some states still use the globalization for their national interests like China, India and South Africa in their major economic initiative that is known as (BRICS).

Last but not the least despite advancements in ICT, AI, cyberspace and Digital platforms but these undermine national regulations by transcending borders in the shape of Cyber-attacks, data flows like India's 2020 app bans (TikTok) and the General Data Protection Regulation(GDPR) in EU mandate data localization to regain state control. But it also transforms states into digital states like

Estonia's e-governance enhancing credibility global integration in 2025. (Makovetska, Varych, 2024) Moreover the rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the shape of ChatGPT, Grok, and Deep seek that has sensitized the states and individuals totally dependent who cannot even use their critical thinking. That's how the rise of globalization alter the nature of state sovereignty through technological advancements.

So in a nutshell, the globalization has not undermined the state sovereignty rather transformed from hawkish nature of state explained by Thomas Hobbes by multiple factors that are explained as economic, political, social and technological through Multilateral Agreements, International Organizations, NGOs, MNCs, TNCs, and Regional Organizations after WW2. Moreover the role of Neo-liberal world in shaping the nature of state through Economy Monitoring institutions IMF, WTO and World Bank. Although globalization has importance to some but also criticized for its selective nature towards specific geography and states like China, North Korea and Iran have not compromised their sovereignty despite facing global isolation. Therefore, one cannot argue that globalization has eroded state autonomy or rather globalization is totally clear and fair.

➤ **Adopting strategies and policies to safeguard the state sovereignty in the context of global pressure.**

The modern states inhibit in a global system to access markets, technology and cooperation on transnational issues but this can also stop states to make decisions. A state might need foreign investment but wants to protect domestic industries and may join international organization on human rights but might face criticism on implementation. Therefore, not defensive adaptive approaches. In distinct dimensions like for political sovereignty states should have control over decision-making without external coercion. Economic sovereignty relates by controlling resources and regulating markets and managing trade relations. Same as cultural sovereignty involves protecting national identity and values, cultural institutions from alien cultures. Same as for security defending territorial integrity and strategic interests within its jurisdiction without external dictation. Which will be explained thoroughly below...

➤ **Strengthening Core Governance and Institutional Resilience**

A state's primary goal must be to establish unified leadership and citizen engagement to counter pressure from international agreements which means that following international laws but not those that damages state's internal immunity through abstentions in global forums like middle powers aligns with one another to resist hegemonic influences. Moreover, avoiding broker political settlements that are rigid and not suitable for domestic affair such as **Dayton Agreement** in Bosnia 1995 that shared the power of Bosnia with Herzegovina brokered by USA. (Lockhart, 2018) states should balance their autonomy by selectively participating in Agreements to get benefits and avoid compromising their power of decision making like China despite the part of organization and getting privileges but when it comes to sovereignty they never allow it .

➤ **Economic Policies for Independence**

Economically states can actively enter into global markets by managing their policies and partners. Moreover, avoid dependencies and focus on the resource management, domestic production which will boost their Economic and Political leverage and focusing Self-reliant growth and advantages to avoid Global risks. (THI MAI, 2021) Domestically states should take steps towards tax collection from TNCs and following social and environmental responsibilities. And also have accountable revenue generating budget to reduce Aid dependency and corruption. Programs like Indonesia's Kecamatan Development Project (KDP) 1998 in which community-driven initiative to prevent poverty through local participation in infrastructure and economic development for jobs and employments.(Lockhart, 2018) Lobbying in a country has negative impact in undermining the autonomy of state's domestic and external affairs like in USA (Jewish, Gun..etc..) lobbies play major role therefore these should be restricted by state to ensure their respective sovereignty. (Makovetska, Varych, 2024)

➤ **Security and Technological Defensive Measures**

In a globalized world the states face the challenges in security or technological threats from other countries or Non-state actors in the shape of terrorism and cyber-attacks. Like domestically the states face terrorism issues from non-state actors

like in Pakistan Tehreek-e-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) has caused many threats to national security and challenging state autonomy. (Pandya, 2025) Therefore, for the states must have control on Hard Power (Military) and non-military (soft power) tools across the politics, economy, defense, and foreign affairs to resist against those states, NGOs, and Organizations that pose threats to state stability or autonomy. Moreover, prioritizing security, law enforcement and resource regulation through peacekeepers that should not include or produce dependency. On the other hand states control on the digital sovereignty frameworks and policies regulating national data, digital infrastructure and algorithmic governance by avoiding external domination in cyber-space and digital governance. (Baidoni, Di Luna, 2025)

Conclusion

The aim of this study has been to explain the complex relationship between globalization and state sovereignty. That has resulted that globalization has not fully eroded rather it has transformed state sovereignty in 21st century. Explained through realist, liberals and constructivist perspectives. Moreover, state sovereignty operates within the world of global economic interdependence, international institutions, normative and technological frameworks. Realists focuses on the primacy of state and liberals emphasize on pooling sovereignty through institutions and constructivists expresses how social norms and beliefs shape state sovereignty. Further it highlights that globalization is selective in nature in which major powers favors their allies and uneven pressure on state from international financial institutions, global markets and security regimes like UNSC, IMF and WTO that exacerbates their vulnerabilities as stated in case studies like Iran and Gaza. However states are not passive victims rather they are the agents voluntarily of pool sovereignty just for collective benefits with global or regional institutions. Lastly By protecting states autonomy amid global pressures by pursuing self-determination economically, politically, and technologically therefore states adopt policies and strategies to avoid dependency and resisting institutional pressures through military and technologically state control over these fields and ensuring that globalization to be used for collective advantages indiscriminately rather than selectively.

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